

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Table S1 – Terms applied to the search strategy.

#1	(database OR databases OR repository OR repositories OR "information system" OR "digital library" OR "virtual library" OR "electronic library" OR "digital catalog" OR "online catalog" OR "electronic catalog" OR "virtual catalog" OR ("web-based" platform) OR ("web-based" resources information) OR "TCM database")
#2	("alternative medicine" OR "alternative therapies" OR "clinical ecology" OR "complementary and alternative healthcare" OR "complementary and alternative medicine" OR "alternative and complementary medicine" OR "complementary medicine" OR "complementary therapies" OR "complementary therapies in medicine" OR "complementary therapies" OR "Integrative medicine" OR "Integrated Medicine" OR "Integrative Therapy" OR "Integrated therapy" OR "Integrative approach" OR "Integrated Approach" OR "Integrative health" OR "Integrated Health" OR "cupping therapy" OR "Cupping Massage" OR "Dry Cupping" OR "Fire-Cupping" OR "Flash Cupping" OR Hijamat OR "Liquid Cupping" OR "Medicinal Cupping" OR "dance therapy" OR "art therapy" OR "Art therapies" OR "Sensory Art Therapies" OR "Drama Therapy" OR "Humor Therapy" OR "dietary supplement" OR "Nutritional supplements" OR "nutritional therapy" OR "health food" OR "Folk Medicine" OR "Folk Remedies" OR "Folk Remedy" OR "Home Remedies" OR "Home Remedy" OR "indigenous knowledge" OR "indigenous medicine" OR "Indigenous Health Systems" OR "integrative medicine" OR "Integrative Oncology" OR "laser therapy" OR "magnetic therapy" OR "music therapy" OR "sound therapy" OR "alexander technique" OR "Alexander therapy" OR "Ozone Therapy" OR "Therapeutic Touch" OR "traditional African medicine" OR "traditional chinese medicine" OR "traditional medicine" OR "medicina tradicional" OR "Primitive Medicine" OR "Traditional Native Healers" OR (massage therap*) OR shantala OR "Massage Therapy" OR acupunctur* OR acupuncture OR "acupuncture therapy" OR electroacupuncture OR acupressure OR "auricular therapy" OR auriculotherapy OR anthroposoph* OR "Anthroposophical medicine" OR "Anthroposophic Medicine" OR aromatherap* OR "volatile oils" OR "aroma therapy" OR aromatherap* OR aromatherapy OR "essential oils" OR "flower remedies" OR "oils essential" OR "oils volatile" OR Ayurved* OR "Ayurvedic medicine" OR Ayurveda OR "Siddha medicine" OR balneotherapy OR balneot* OR hydrotherapy OR biofeedback OR "Psychology Biofeedback" OR chiropract* OR chiropractic OR "manipulation chiropractic" OR "manipulation osteopathic" OR Ethnomedicine OR homeopath* OR "homeopathic agent" OR "homeopathic agents" OR "homeopathic drugs" OR homeopathy OR homoeopath* OR hypnosis OR hypnotherap* OR hypnotherapy OR imagery OR meditation OR mindfulness OR naprapathy OR naturopath* OR naturopathy OR "Naturopathic Medicine" OR "Nature Therapies" OR "Nature Therapy" OR ecotherapy OR Ecotherapies OR osteopath* OR osteopathy OR "Osteopatic Therapy" OR "Osteopathic Manipulation" OR phytotherapy OR phytom* OR phytoter* OR "medicinal plants" OR "plant extracts" OR "plant medicinal" OR "plants medicinal" OR "Plant-Based Medicines" OR "Floral Therapy" OR "Pine-Bark Extract" OR "Plant Extracts" OR "Plant Oils" OR "Plant-Based Medications" OR "plantas medicinai" OR herbal* OR "herbal medicine" OR "Herbal Therapy" OR "Herb Therapy" OR Reflexolog* OR reflexology OR reflexotherapy OR relaxation OR "relaxation techniques" OR "relaxation training" OR shiatsu OR "Tai Chi" OR "Qi Gong" OR "mind body" OR "Mind-Body Therapies" OR Unani OR "Unani medicine" OR yoga OR moxibustion OR Apitherapy OR "Guided Imagery")
#3	#1 AND #2

Supplementary Table S2 – Included references.

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151	Scott JM, Lindsey AT, Costello RB, Deuster PA. Using the Dietary Supplement Label Database to Identify Potentially Harmful Dietary Supplement Ingredients. <i>Nutr Today</i> . 2018 Sep-Oct;53(5):229-233. doi: 10.1097/NT.0000000000000295.
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Supplementary Table S4 – Distribution of databases by TCIM (sub-)areas.

Sub-Areas	Digital sources (n)	Country	Definition
Traditional Medicine (n = 93)			
Ayurveda	5	India ^{5, 13, 31, 45, 106}	System of Traditional Medicine from India.
AYUSH	3	India ^{14, 106, 124}	Systems of healthcare from Ministry Ayush that encompass Ayurveda, Yoga, Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, Sowa-Rigpa and Homoeopathy.
Kampo Medicine	3	Japan ^{118, 119, 120}	System of traditional herbal medical from Japan.
Medicinal Plants	47	Bangladesh ⁶⁸ , Belgium ⁴⁰ , China ^{15, 18, 26, 30, 41, 43, 46, 50, 52, 69, 78, 99, 105, 114} , Egypt ³⁸ , Ethiopia ⁴² , Germany ¹¹ , India ^{5, 9, 33, 57, 75, 85, 87, 106, 113, 122, 123, 124} , Latin America ¹⁰⁸ , Romania ⁸⁴ , Russia ¹⁰⁴ , Singapore ⁶⁶ , South Africa ⁹⁰ , South Korea ¹⁰⁷ , Spain ¹⁹ , Thailand ^{49, 62} , United States ^{1, 12, 48, 51, 63, 93} , Vietnam ¹¹¹	Phytotherapy, many herbal medicine practices are transmitted orally in various traditional cultures (12).
Traditional Medicine	5	China ⁵⁹ , Latin America and the Caribbean Countries ⁶⁷ , Malaysia ⁴⁴ , Philippine ¹²⁵ , and the USA ²⁷	
Traditional Chinese Medicine	24	China ^{2, 15, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 30, 32, 41, 47, 58, 95, 96, 97, 101, 102, 103, 112, 115} , Germany ⁹¹ , Singapore ¹⁰⁰ , South Korea ¹⁰⁷ and the USA ⁸⁸	Includes acupuncture, herbal medicine, and practices (12).
Traditional Iranian Medicine	1	Iran ¹⁰⁹	
Traditional Japanese Medicine	1	South Korea ^{83, 107}	Includes acupuncture, herbal medicine, and practices (12).
Traditional Thai Medicine	1	Thailand ⁶²	Includes acupuncture, herbal medicine, and practices (12).
Traditional Vietnamese Medicine	1	Vietnam ¹¹¹	
Unani Medicine	2	India ¹⁰⁶ and Germany ²⁹	Yūnānī means 'Greek', referring to the fact that the Perso-Arabic system of medicine was based on the teachings of the Greek physicians. Currently practiced mainly in countries of the Middle East and South Asia it has its bases in ancient texts of Greek and Arabic origin (12).

Sub-Areas	Digital sources (n)	Country	Definition
Indigenous Medicine (n = 5)			
Native American Ethnobotany ⁷² and Native Health Database ⁷³	2	USA	
NPM New Zealand's Māori Centre of Research Excellence ⁷⁹	1	New Zealand	
MPDB 2.0 Indigenous Medicinal Plants Database Bangladesh ⁶⁸	1	Bangladesh	
Indigenous People's Health Repository in the PAHO/WHO Virtual Health Library ⁸⁹	1	Brazil	
Complementary and Integrative Medicine Therapies (n = 52)			
Acupuncture	1	United Kingdom ³⁹	widely used as a complementary treatment in the West, although originating in Traditional Chinese Medicine (12).
Anthroposophic Medicine	2	Spain ^{7, 65}	an integrative medical system, an extension of biomedicine incorporating a holistic approach to man and nature and to illness and healing. It was founded in the early 1920s by Rudolf Steiner and Ita Wegman (12). It is established in 80 countries worldwide, most significantly in Central Europe and South America (20).
Art Therapy	1	Germany ¹⁰	The use of artistic activities as a form of therapy.
Chiropractic practices	1	Australia ⁵⁶	The spinal manipulation to treat and prevent disorders (12).
Complementary and Integrative Medicine	2	Germany ¹⁷ and the USA ⁴	
Complementary and Integrative Medicine and Traditional Medicine	3	#LILACS Region ⁶⁶ , in Malaysia ⁴⁴ and the USA ²⁷	
Complementary and Integrative	1	USA ⁷⁴	

Sub-Areas	Digital sources (n)	Country	Definition
Medicine, Dietary Supplements and Natural Products			
Dietary Supplements	4	USA ^{20, 34, 35, 36}	
Holistic Medicine and Therapies	2	Germany ¹¹⁶ and USA ³	
Homeopathy	5	Brazil ⁵⁴ , Canada ⁵⁵ and Germany ^{28, 53, 110}	A therapeutic system that is based on the theory of ‘similars’ (12).
Integrative Oncology	6	Canada ⁶⁰ , China ¹⁸ , India ⁷⁷ , Norway ¹⁶ and the USA ^{1, 37}	Where complementary therapies, such as integrative nutrition and psychological support, are incorporated into conventional cancer treatment (12).
Natural Products	21	Brazil ⁸⁰ , China ^{78, 86} , Germany ^{6, 92} , India ^{64, 77, 94, 106} , Iran ¹⁰⁹ , Singapore ⁶⁶ , South Africa ⁹⁰ , Spain ⁷¹ and the USA ^{8, 37, 61, 63, 70, 74, 76, 93}	
Osteopathy	2	Germany ⁸¹ and the USA ⁸²	
Yoga	1	United Kingdom ¹¹⁷	

Latin American and Caribbean Center on Health Sciences Information (BIREME/PAHO/WHO).

¹⁻¹²⁵TCIM digital resources numbering from **Table 3**.

Supplementary Table S5 – List of excluded resources with reason for exclusion.

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
1	1KP dataset - ONEKP	Not primarily TCIM	https://db.cngb.org/onekp/	52
2	3DMET	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.3dmet.dna.affrc.go.jp/	52
3	ACNPD - Anti-cancer natural product database	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.acnpd-fu.com/	88
4	ACUBRIEFS	Database is not operational	https://acubriefs.blogspot.com/	7
5	AfroCancer - African Anticancer Natural Products Library	No access to resource	https://african-compounds.org/about/afrocancer/	52
6	AfroDB - a collection of natural products from African medicinal plants with known bioactivities	Merged with other resource	https://african-compounds.org/about/afrodb/	52
7	Afrotryp - African Antitrypanosoma Natural Products Library	Merged with other resource	https://african-compounds.org/about/afrotryp/	52
8	Alkamid database	Website could not be retrieved	http://alkamid.ugent.be/	52
9	ANTIPSEUDOBASE: Database of Antimicrobial Peptides and Essential Oils Against Pseudomonas	Website could not be retrieved	http://bims.pasteur.tn:3838/APP/	90
10	AntiSMASH	Not primarily TCIM	http://antismash.secondarymetabolites.org/	52
11	ATDB database	Website could not be retrieved	http://protchem.hunnu.edu.cn/toxin	52
12	National Genomics Data Center (NGDC)	Not primarily TCIM	https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn/	52
13	BiGG	Not primarily TCIM	http://bigg.ucsd.edu	52
14	BindingDB	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.bindingdb.org/bind/index.jsp	52
15	BIOFACQUIM	Website could not be retrieved	https://biofacquim.herokuapp.com/	52
16	BioPhytMol	Website could not be retrieved	http://ab-openlab.csir.res.in/biophytmol	52
17	BMRB	Not primarily TCIM	https://bmr.io/	52
18	BOLD	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.boldsystems.org/	52
19	Brazilian Pharmacopoeia Genomic Database (BPGD)	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.bpgenome.com	95
20	BRENDA Enzyme Database	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.brenda-enzymes.org/	52
21	CAM on PubMed	Merged with other resource	www.nlm.nih.gov/nccam/camonpubmed.html	7

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
22	CamMedNP - Cameroonian Medicinal Plant and Natural Products Database	No access to resource	https://african-compounds.org/about/cammednp/	52
23	CAMP	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.camp.bicnirrh.res.in/	52
24	Carotenoids Database	Website could not be retrieved	http://carotenoiddbjp	52
25	CCMRD - Complex Carbohydrate Magnetic Resonance Database	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.ccmrd.org/	52
26	CEMTD - Chinese Ethnic Minority Traditional Drug	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.cemtd.com/index.html	91
27	Chang Gung Research Database (CGRD)	Not primarily TCIM	https://cghdpt.cgmh.org.tw/en/dept/3S0R0/m/5779/page/12115	87
28	ChEBI	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/init.do	52
29	Chem!Dplus	Not primarily TCIM	https://chem.nlm.nih.gov/chemidplus/	52
30	ChemBank	Website could not be retrieved	http://chembank.broad.harvard.edu/	52
31	ChEMBL database	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/	52
32	ChemDP	Website could not be retrieved	http://chemdp.com	52
33	ChemSpider	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.chemspider.com/	52
34	China Information Service System on Traditional Chinese Medicine	Website could not be retrieved	nricm1.nricm.edu.tw/textdb.php	50
35	China Traditional Chinese Medicine Patent Database	Website could not be retrieved	www.sipo.gov.cn/sipo_English/xxcp_e/ctpd/t20030304_12199.htm	50
36	Chinese Virtual Herbarium	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.cvh.ac.cn/index.php	52
37	CHMDB	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.meandgi.com/herb-database	52
38	CHMIS-C - Comprehensive Herbal Medicine Information System for Cancer	Website could not be retrieved	sw16.im.med.umich.edu/chmis-c/	7
39	CloudPhar TCM Database	Website could not be retrieved	http://cloud.tasly.com/#/tcm/home	44
40	CMap	Not primarily TCIM	https://clue.io/	52
41	CNKI - China National Knowledge Infrastructure	Not primarily TCIM	www.cnki.net https://oversea.cnki.net/index/	50
42	COCONUT - the COlleCtion of Open NatUral producTs	Not primarily TCIM	https://coconut.naturalproducts.net	52

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
43	ConMedNP - Congo Basin Medicinal Plant and Natural Products Database	No access to resource	https://plants.ensembl.org/index.html	52
44	CPMCP - China Traditional Medicine Patent	Website could not be retrieved	http://cpmcp.top/chmp.cnipr.cn/tcm_patent1/englishversion/login/index.asp	7
45	CPPsite	Not primarily TCIM	https://webs.iiitd.edu.in/raghava/cppsite	52
46	CSLS - Chemical Structure Lookup Service	Not primarily TCIM	http://cactus.nci.nih.gov/cgi-bin/lookup/search	52
47	cTD - Comparative Toxicogenomics Database	Not primarily TCIM	http://ctdbase.org/	52
48	Customary Medicinal Knowledge Base	Website could not be retrieved	https://biolinfo.org/cmkb/index.php	7
49	CVDHD Cardiovascular Disease Herbal Medicine	Website could not be retrieved	http://pkuxxj.pku.edu.cn/CVDHD	44
50	CWMIIN - Drug Herb Interaction	Not updated	https://dhi.cmu.edu.tw/query/	52
51	D3AI-CoV	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.d3pharma.com/D3Targets-2019-nCoV/D3AI-CoV/index.php	52
52	Database of HSR Citations	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.hsr.d.research.va.gov/research/citations/default.cfm	manual search
53	DBAASP - Database of Antimicrobial Activity and Structure of Peptides	Not primarily TCIM	https://dbaasp.org/	52
54	dbAMPs	Not primarily TCIM	https://awi.cuhk.edu.cn/dbAMP/index.php	52
55	DEREP	Merged with other resource		28
56	DiaMedBase	Link does not work	http://www.progenebio.in/DMP/DMP	86
57	DIDB	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.druginteractionsolutions.org/solutions/clinical-datasets/	52
58	DisGeNET	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.disgenet.org/	52
59	Dissertation and Thesis Abstract System	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.lib.umi.com/dissertations	50
60	DRAMP - Data repository of antimicrobial peptides	Not primarily TCIM	http://dramp.cpu-bioinform.org/	52
61	DrugBank	Not primarily TCIM	https://go.drugbank.com/	52
62	Dúchas - Irish National Folklore Ethnography Database	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.duchas.ie/en	96

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
63	EANPDB - Eastern African Natural Products Database	Merged with other resource	http://african-compounds.org/nanpdb/	52
64	Ensembl	Not primarily TCIM	http://asia.ensembl.org/index.html	52
65	Ensembl Plants	Not primarily TCIM	https://plants.ensembl.org/index.html	52
66	EXTRACT DATABASE	Website could not be retrieved	www.plant-medicine.com/grades/extract/main-menu.asp	7
67	FAOLEX database	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.fao.org/faolex/en/	manual search
68	GenBank	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/	52
69	GeneCards - The Human Gene Database	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.genecards.org/	52
70	GlycoMaps	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.glycosciences.de/modeling/glycomapsdb/	52
71	GlycoNAVI	Not primarily TCIM	https://glyconavi.org/	52
72	GlyTouCan	Not primarily TCIM	https://glytoucan.org/	52
73	GMD	Not primarily TCIM	http://gmd.mpimp-golm.mpg.de/	52
74	GNPS - Global Natural Products Social Molecular Networking	Not primarily TCIM	https://gnps.ucsd.edu/	52
75	GO - Gene Ontology	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.geneontology.org/	52
76	HerbalDB 2.0 Indonesian medicinal plant database	No access to resource		97
77	HerDing	Website could not be retrieved	http://combio.gist.ac.kr/herding	52
78	HIM	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.bioinformatics.org.cn/	52
79	HMDB	Not primarily TCIM	https://hmdb.ca/	52
80	Hom-Inform - British Homeopathic Library	Not updated	https://hom-inform.org/	7
81	Homeopathy Clinical Trials	Merged with other resource	https://www.ikim.unibe.ch/forschung/fachbereiche/klassische_homoeopathie_potenzierte_substanzen/homeopathy_clinical_trials/index_ger.html	23
82	HomeoWeb	Website could not be retrieved	www.antenna.nl/homeoweb	7

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
83	HOMIS - Homeopathic Intervention Studies	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.ikim.unibe.ch/forschung/fachbereiche/klassische_homoeopathie_potenzierte_substanzen/homeopathy_clinical_trials/index_ger.html	23
84	HPM - Human Proteome Map	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.humanproteomemap.org	52
85	IBIS: Integrative BodyMind Information System	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.ouribis.com/	28
86	Indonesian Medicinal Plant Database	Website could not be retrieved	http://herbaldb.farmasi.ui.ac.id	98
87	INMEDPLAN - Indian Medicinal Plants Distributed Databases Network	Website could not be retrieved	http://ece.iisc.ernet.in/ernet-members/frlht.html#inmedplan	28
88	InPACdb	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.inpacdb.org	52
89	Intelligent Plant Database	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.iplant.cn/	52
90	KEGG	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.genome.ad.jp/kegg/kegg2.html	52
91	KNApSAcK	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.knapsackfamily.com/KNApSAcK_Family/	52
92	Korea Barcode of Life database	Website could not be retrieved	http://koreabarcode.org	52
93	Lexicomp Online	Not primarily TCIM	http://webstore.lexi.com/Store/ONLINE	52
94	LIPID MAPS	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.lipidmaps.org/	52
95	LipidBank	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.lipidbank.jp/	52
96	LipidHome	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/apweiler-srv/lipidhome	52
97	LipidIMMS Analyzer	Website could not be retrieved	http://imms.zhulab.cn/LipidIMMS/	52
98	LipidPedia	Not primarily TCIM	http://lipidpedia.cmdm.tw	52
99	LTKB - Liver Toxicity Knowledge Base	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.fda.gov/science-research/bioinformatics-tools/liver-toxicity-knowledge-base-ltkb	89
100	LTM-TCM	Website could not be retrieved	http://cloud.tasly.com/#/tcm/home	44
101	MarinLit	Not primarily TCIM	https://marinlit.rsc.org/	52
102	Medflor India/ABIM	Website could not be retrieved	www.indianmedicine.eldoc.ub.rug.nl/root/R/95965/?pFullItemRecord=ON	28

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
103	Medherb	Website could not be retrieved	http://medicinalherbs.comule.com/	52
104	MedPServer	Website could not be retrieved	http://bif.uohyd.ac.in/medserver/	99
105	Merck Index online	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.rsc.org/Merck-Index/	52
106	MetaboHunter	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.nrcbioinformatics.ca/metabohunter/	52
107	MetaboLights	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/	52
108	MetaCyc	Not primarily TCIM	http://metacyc.org/	52
109	MetIDB	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.metidb.org/	52
110	METLIN	Not primarily TCIM	https://metlin.scripps.edu	52
111	MIBiG - Minimum Information about a Biosynthetic Gene cluster	Not primarily TCIM	https://mibig.secondarymetabolites.org/	52
112	MoNA	Not primarily TCIM	https://mona.fiehnlab.ucdavis.edu/	52
113	MPDB - Moroccan Natural Phyto-Compounds DataBase	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.mpdb.org/default.php	93
114	MyTKDL - Malaysia Traditional Knowledge Digital Library	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.myipo.gov.my/en/malaysia-traditional-knowledge-digital-library-mytkdl/	Living review
115	mzCloud	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.mzcloud.org/	52
116	MZedDB?	Website could not be retrieved	http://maltese.dbs.aber.ac.uk:8888/hrmet/index.html	52
117	NANPDB - Northern African Natural Products Database	Merged with other resource	http://african-compounds.org/nanpdb/	52
118	NAPRALERT - Natural Products ALERT	Database is not operational	https://pharmacognosy.pharmacy.uic.edu/napralert/	7
119	National Animal Collection Resource Center	Not primarily TCIM	http://museum.ioz.ac.cn/index.html	52
120	National Research Institute of Chinese Medicine	Website could not be retrieved	nricm1.nricm.edu.tw/textdb.php	50
121	Natural Medicines Comprehensive Database	Website could not be retrieved	https://naturalmedicines.therapeuticresearch.com/	19
122	Natural Standard	Merged with other resource	http://www.naturalstandard.com	100

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
123	NCBI	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	52
124	NeMedPlant	Website could not be retrieved	http://bif.uohyd.ac.in/nemedplant/	52
125	NHANES-DSD Dietary Supplement Database	Merged with other resource	https://wwwn.cdc.gov/nchs/nhanes/search/datapage.aspx?Component=Dietary&CycleBeginYear=2011	61
126	NMRshiftDB	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.nmrshiftdb.org	52
127	OMIM - An Online Catalog of Human Genes and Genetic Disorders	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.omim.org/	52
128	OncoRX	Website could not be retrieved	www.onco-informatics.com	7
129	OTSeeker - Occupational Therapy Systematic Evaluation of Evidence	Not primarily TCIM	www.otseeker.com	7
130	p-ANAPL library	No access to resource	https://african-compounds.org/about/p-anapl/	52
131	PDB	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.rcsb.org/	52
132	PDBBind	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.pdbbind.org.cn/	52
133	PDTD	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.dddc.ac.cn/pdtd	52
134	PEdro - Physiotherapy Evidence Database	Not primarily TCIM	www.pedro.org.au	7
135	PepBank	Website could not be retrieved	http://pepbank.mgh.harvard.edu/	52
136	PepQSAR	Not primarily TCIM	http://i.uestc.edu.cn/PQsarDB	52
137	PharmGKB	Not primarily TCIM	https://www.pharmgkb.org	52
138	Phytochemica	Website could not be retrieved	http://home.iitj.ac.in/~bagler/webserver/Phytochemica	52
139	PHYTODOK	Not primarily TCIM	https://en.lbst.dk/	28
140	Plant	Website could not be retrieved	www.brazilian-plants.com	7
141	Plant Database of India	Website could not be retrieved	http://221.135.191.194/plantsindia/index.php	7
142	PlantMarkers	Website could not be retrieved	markers.btk.fi	7
143	ProNAB database	Not primarily TCIM	https://web.iitm.ac.in/bioinfo2/pronab/	52
144	PubChem	Not primarily TCIM	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	52
145	RAACFDdb - Rheumatoid Arthritis Ayurvedic Classical Formulations Database	Website could not be retrieved	www.beta.vit.ac.in/raacfdb/index.html	101

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
146	Reactome Knowledgebase	Not primarily TCIM	https://reactome.org	52
147	Reaxys	Chemistry database	https://www.reaxys.com/#/search/quick	52
148	RefSeq	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/	52
149	ReSpect	End of service, no longer available	http://spectra.psc.riken.jp/	52
150	SciFinder	Chemistry database	https://scifinder.cas.org	52
151	SDBS	Not primarily TCIM	https://sdfs.db.aist.go.jp	52
152	SerpentinaDB	Website could not be retrieved	http://home.iitj.ac.in/~bagler/webserver/SerpentinaDB/	52
153	SMPDB	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.smpdb.ca/	52
154	SoFDA	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.tcmip.cn/Syndrome/front/#/	52
155	SOMEPEP	No access to resource		28
156	Spektraris-NMR	Not primarily TCIM	http://langelabtools.wsu.edu/nmr/	52
157	STITCH	Not primarily TCIM	http://stitch.embl.de/	52
158	StraPep - a structural database of biological peptide-mediated interactions	Not primarily TCIM	http://huanglab.phys.hust.edu.cn/pepdb/	52
159	STRING	Not primarily TCIM	https://string-db.org/	52
160	SuperToxic	Not primarily TCIM	http://bioinformatics.charite.de/supertoxic	52
161	SWEETLEAD	Not primarily TCIM	https://simtk.org/home/sweetlead	52
162	SwissLipids	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.swisslipids.org/	52
163	TCM-CED	No access to resource		92
164	TCM-Information	Website could not be retrieved	tcm.cz3.nus.edu.sg	7
165	TCM-Mesh	Website could not be retrieved	http://mesh.tcm.microbioinformatics.org/	52
166	TCMGeneDIT	Website could not be retrieved	tcm.lifescience.ntu.edu.tw	7
167	TCMID Traditional Chinese Medicine Integrated	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.megabionet.org/tmid	manual search
168	TCMKSP	Not primarily TCIM	https://gb.tcm.cnki.net/	52
169	TCMLARS - Traditional Chinese Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.cintcm.com/index.html http://www.cintcm.com http://www.sinomd.com	7

#	Name	Reason	URL	Reference Table S3
170	Thai TKDL (TTKDL)	Website could not be retrieved	https://ttdkl.dtam.moph.go.th/	Living review
171	TID	Not primarily TCIM	https://db.idrblab.net/ttd/	52
172	TMDB	Website could not be retrieved	http://pcsb.ahau.edu.cn:8080/TCDB/index.jsp	52
173	TPPT	Website could not be retrieved	https://www.agroscope.admin.ch/agroscope/en/home/publications/apps/tppt.html	52
174	TRADIMed	Website could not be retrieved	www.tradimed.com	7
175	Traditional Chinese Medicine Online	Website could not be retrieved	http://www.cintcm.com/e_cintcm/index.thm	50
176	TriForC	Not primarily TCIM	http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/triforc/	52
177	UniCarb-DB - The Glycomic MS Database and Repository	Not primarily TCIM	https://unicarb-db.expasy.org/	52
178	UniProt	Not primarily TCIM	http://www.uniprot.org/	52
179	UNPD	Website could not be retrieved	http://pkuxxj.pku.edu.cn/UNPD	52
180	YaTCM - Yet another Traditional Chinese Medicine database	Link does not work	http://cadd.pharmacy.nankai.edu.cn/yatcm/home	44
181	ZINC	Chemistry database	https://zinc15.docking.org/	52

Supplementary Material S1 – Specialists Consultation Survey Questions

WHO Global Repository on Traditional, Complementary, and Integrative Medicine (TCIM) and Indigenous Knowledge (IK)

We invite you to contribute to identifying information sources/resources that index and facilitate access to information on Traditional, Complementary, and Integrative Medicine and Indigenous Knowledge, such as: Databases; Repositories; Virtual/Digital Libraries; Scientific Journals; Pharmacopeia, etc. *obligatory fields.

1. E-mail *

[Open text field]

2. Name of the information resource/source on TCIM/IK *

[Open text field]

3. Link to access (URL) the information resource/source *

[Open text field]

4. Type of information resource/source * (select only one):

- Bibliographic Database
- Repository
- Virtual/Digital Library
- Scientific Journal

- Catalog, Directory
- Pharmacopoeia
- Other

5. Select one or more domains that (may apply regarding) the information source may be related to:

- Health and wellbeing
- Evidence-based health interventions
- Research priorities and research methodologies
- ICD 11 integrated routine health information based on real-world data (use cases/safety/outcomes)
- Biodiversity and natural products
- Sustainability and planetary health
- Digital health landscapes
- Policy landscapes
- Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Other

6. What is the country or region for the information resource/source? *

[Open text field]

7. Which area(s) is the information resource/source related to? (Select all that apply)

- Complementary and Integrative Medicine
- Indigenous medicine - Folk medicine - Indigenous Knowledge
- Traditional Medicine (in general)
- Acupuncture
- Anthroposophical Medicine
- Ayurveda Medicine
- Biodiversity
- Body-Mind Therapies – Art Therapy, Hypnosis, Mindfulness, Relaxation, Yoga, etc
- Chinese Traditional Medicine
- Energy Therapies - Cupping therapy, Reiki, Floral therapy, etc
- Homeopathy
- Manual Therapies - Osteopathy, Chiropractic care, Shiatzu, Massage, etc
- Medicinal Plants, Phytotherapy, Herbal Medicine
- Naturopathy
- Siddha Medicine
- Unani Medicine
- Natural Products - Supplements, Apitherapy, Aromatherapy, etc.

8. Use this space to complement or specify something about the information resource/ source.

[Open text field]

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